

11-16 AUGUST 2019
22nd International Conference
on Composite Materials

Thermo-mechanical behaviour of microwave-cured carbon nanotubes- based polymer composites

¹Gaurav Arora and ²Himanshu Pathak

^{1,2}School of Engineering, Indian Institute of Technology, Mandi, Himachal Pradesh, India-175005

Corresponding author: himanshu@iitmandi.ac.in

CONFERENCE
HOSTS:

CONFERENCE
DESTINATION
SUPPORTERS:

#ICCM22

Objectives

- To cure the pellets of low-density polyethylene/CNT and HDPE/CNT using 1100 kW microwave applicator.
- To study the change in tensile strength, Young's modulus and critical stress intensity factor with respect to increase in temperature tested using ASTM D3039 and D5045 for tension and fracture toughness of microwave cured composites.
- To study the fractography of elevated temperature tested specimen in order to understand the failure mechanism.

Introduction

- Thermoplastics are ductile, poor creep resistant, tougher and usually exists in semi-crystalline or in amorphous phase and on heating beyond the T_m or T_g , they lose their structure to more deformable and flexible structure.
- Polymer composites possess improved properties such as tensile/impact strength, stiffness, wear resistance, thermal conductivity, thermal insulation, corrosion resistance, weight/temperature dependent behaviour and fatigue life.
- Thermomechanical behaviour and thermal stability of thermosetting polymers and their composites are quite adequate to be used for varied applications ranging from coatings, electronics, packaging, adhesives fiber reinforced composites, structural components in aircraft and aerospace industries.

Materials

Phase	Multi-walled CNTs	Low density polyethylene(LDPE)	High density polyethylene(LDPE)
Young's Modulus	50 GPa	0.98 GPa	1.2 GPa
Poisson ratio	0.26	0.4	0.46
Density	2100 kg/m ³	920 kg/m ³	950 kg/m ³
Average diameter	15 nm	---	---
Average length	15 μm	---	---

Table 1. Individual properties of CNTs and polymers used.

Fig.1. Pellets of polymer/CNT composites
(**Procured from Chengdu Organic Chemicals Ltd. China**)

Mechanism of microwave processing

Tensile & fracture toughness specimen

Fig.2. Mechanism of processing of polymer/CNT composites

Aims after fabrication

Mechanical characterizations at room and elevated temperature

- Tensile testing
- Fracture toughness

Fig.3. Fractured specimen after tensile testing

Fig.4. Fracture toughness tested specimen

Results and discussion

Fig.5. Strain-stress curve of LDPE/CNT composites

Fig.6. Strain-stress curve of HDPE/CNT composites

Variation of UTS and YM w.r.t temperature

Fig.7. Effect of temperature on UTS of the composites

Fig.8. Effect of temperature on Young's modulus (YM) of the composites

Variation of K_{IC} w.r.t temperature

Calculation and validation procedure of K_{IC} of the composites using ASTM standard D5045

$$K_{IC} = K_Q = \left(\frac{P_Q}{BW^{1/2}} \right) f(x), \quad W = 2B$$

$$f(x) = 6x^{1/2} \frac{[1.99 - x(1-x)(2.15 - 3.93x + 2.7x^2)]}{(1+2x)(1-x)^{3/2}}, \quad x = \frac{a}{W}$$

$$B, a, (W - a) \geq 2.5 \left(\frac{K_Q}{\sigma_{YS}} \right)$$

Fig.9. Effect of temperature on fracture toughness of the composites

Optical microscopic images

Fig.10. Optical image of tensile tested (left) and fracture toughness tested specimen (right)

Scanning electron microscopic (SEM) images

Fig.11. SEM of fracture toughness tested (left) and tensile tested (right) specimen

Scanning electron microscopic (SEM) images

Fig.12. SEM of room temperature (left) and high temperature (right) tested specimen

Conclusions

- Microwave processed thermoplastic composites were tested successfully under thermo-mechanical environment.
- HDPE/CNT composites has shown more resistance to deformation and elongated more compared to LDPE/CNT composites.
- Remarkable decrease in Young's modulus and tensile strength has been observed with increase in temperature. Young's modulus of HDPE/CNT composites has decreased from 7.86 GPa to 2.47 GPa with increase in temperature from room to 100 °C whereas tensile strength has decreased from 20.3 MPa to 6.51 MPa. In case of LDPE/CNT composites, Young's modulus and tensile strength has decreased from 2.56 GPa to 0.062 GPa and 11 MPa to 1.51 MPa, respectively with increase in temperature from room to 100 °C.
- Fracture toughness of HDPE/CNT composites is higher compared to LDPE/CNT composites. K_{IC} of HDPE/CNT and LDPE/CNT composites has decreased from 1.811 MPa m^{1/2} to 0.261 MPa m^{1/2} and 1.447 MPa m^{1/2} to 0.071 MPa m^{1/2}, respectively with increase in temperature from room to 100 °C.
- SEM examinations has revealed the failure of composite by debonding of CNTs and fracture of CNTs at the interface.

References

- Mishra RR and Sharma AK. Microwave-material interaction phenomena: Heating mechanisms, challenges and opportunities in material processing. *Compos Part A Appl Sci Manuf* 2016; 81: 78–97.
- Fotiou I *et al.* Microwave curing of epoxy polymers reinforced with carbon nanotubes. *J Appl Polym Sci* 2013; 129: 2754–2764.
- Chang J *et al.* The production of carbon nanotube/epoxy composites with a very high dielectric constant and low dielectric loss by microwave curing. *Carbon N Y* 2012; 50: 689–698.
- Mittal G *et al.* A review on carbon nanotubes and graphene as fillers in reinforced polymer nanocomposites. *J Ind Eng Chem* 2015; 21: 11–25.
- Aalaie J *et al.* Preparation and Characterization of Linear Low-Density Polyethylene/Carbon Nanotube Nanocomposites. *J Macromol Sci Part B Phys* 2007; 46: 877–889.
- Gupta M, Leong EWW. *Microwaves and Metals*. John Wiley & Sons, 2007.
- Kanagaraj S *et al.* Mechanical properties of high-density polyethylene/carbon nanotube composites, *Compos. Sci. Technol.* 67 (2007) 3071–3077.
- Grabbert N *et al.* Mechanical and electrical properties of low density polyethylene filled with carbon nanotubes Related content Mechanical Properties of Individual Composite Poly(methyl-methacrylate)-Multiwalled Carbon Nanotubes Nanofibers n.d.
- Su B *et al.* Influence of mechanical properties of polypropylene/low-density polyethylene nanocomposites. *Nanomater Nanotechnol* 2017;7:184798041771592.
- Arora *et al.* Fabrication and characterization of microwave cured high-density polyethylene/carbon nanotube and polypropylene/carbon nanotube composites. *J Compos Mater* 2019; 53: 2091-2104.
- Arora G and Pathak H. Modeling of transversely isotropic properties of CNT-polymer composites using meso-scale FEM approach. *Compos Part B* 2019; 166: 588-597.

THANK YOU

ICCM22
MELBOURNE
AUSTRALIA

11-16 AUGUST 2019
22nd International Conference
on Composite Materials

#ICCM22